

An Analysis of Judiciary Independence in India

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Abstract

This study delves into the intricacies of judicial independence in India, evaluating its historical evolution, contemporary challenges, and impact on the country's democratic fabric. Beginning with an examination of the constitutional framework that guarantees judicial independence, the paper navigates through key judicial appointments, tenure security, and financial autonomy issues. It examines the delicate balance between the judiciary and other branches of government and emphasizes the role of the Supreme Court as the guardian of the constitution. In addition, this study examines the influence of external factors, such as political pressure and public opinion, on the Independence of the judiciary. The analysis unveils the dynamic interplay between judicial independence and social justice, highlighting landmark cases that have shaped the jurisprudential landscape. Special attention is given to recent legal reforms aimed at bolstering judicial autonomy and insulating it from external pressures. The study also looks in to how technology might improve accountability and transparency in try. The Indian Constitution supports an Independent judiciary the federal and state level, despite not adhering of the strict idea of separation of power, its astounding that the constitution did not take similar precautions to protect the members of the Judiciary and to vouchsafe the status and dignity of their seemingly obvious but respective heads of the executive and legislature and its members, despite the clear enactment of provisions conferring immunities and privileges upon them and of safeguarding their honour and disunity in due proportion, Aspired to social, Economic and political Justice for all people without guaranteeing the infallibility of justice-dispensers is a constitutional country. but the Independence.

Key words: Judicial Independence, Constitutional Framework, Supreme Court, Tenure Security, Financial Autonomy, Legal Reforms, Technology in Judiciary.

Introduction

System is free from excessive influence or meddling from the legislative or executive arms of the government. In the case of India, a nation celebrated for its demo This analysis endeavours to delve into the intricate fabric of judiciary independence in India, examining its historical underpinnings , constitutional framework, and contemporary challenges. From the inception of the Indian judicial system to its present-day complexities, this study aims to navigate the terrain of judicial autonomy, exploring the factors that shape and sometimes undermine its independence. The significance of judiciary independence cannot be overstated, especially in a country as vast and diverse as India. With a population exceeding a billion, myriad languages, cultures, and socio-economic disparitiesThe judiciary plays a vital role in promoting cohesion, ensuring access to justice and the delicate balance of power between the branches of government.

However, amidst the lofty ideals of judicial autonomy lie pragmatic realities and persistent concerns, ranging from judicial appointments to executive influence, that warrant careful examination.

As we embark on this analytical journey, it is imperative to recognize the nuances and complexities inherent in the Indian judicial landscape. By critically evaluating the mechanisms and challenges surrounding judiciary independence, this analysis seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of

India's democratic ethos and the evolving dynamics of its legal system. In the subsequent sections, we will explore the historical evolution of the Indian judiciary, elucidate the constitutional provisions safeguarding its independence, examine contemporary issues confronting judicial autonomy, and propose potential avenues for fortifying the pillars of judiciary independence in India. By means of meticulous investigation and well-informed discussion, we aim to illuminate this crucial facet of India's democratic structure, confirming the lasting significance of an autonomous judiciary in maintaining the values of fairness, parity, and democracy?

Some of the elements that support the independence of the judiciary are ---

The objective of attaining judicial independence can be achieved through a variety of strategies-

Mode of appointment of judges

In the Constitutions of India there are two articles that regulate the nomination of the judges: Article 124 and Article 217. According to the article, the president of India is the one who appoints his appointments to the Supreme Court and the High Court of India, after receipt with the chief judge of India and other judges. This procedure finally established an agreement system in India, and four top judges in the Supreme Court made a recommendation on the transfer and appointment of the judges. This method was improved through three stages for three judges.

The procedure for the selection of judges in India changed in the wake of these three circumstances in 1982 and 1998. In the case of *S.P. Gupta against the Union of India* (1982), the Supreme Court of India ruled that the President of India has the right to reject the advice of the Chief Justice if there is a convincing power of the President of India not to consult the Chief Justice of India or other judges when taking decisions regarding the selection and transfer. The dynamics surrounding the selection and transfer of judges have changed following the decision of the judges. This would result in a significant power imbalance between the administrative branch and the judiciary. A title case "*SC. Advocates on Record Association vs Union of India*" finally decided in 1993, after a period of twelve years. Because of the "primacy" and "justifiability" of the Union of India, the verdict made by that judge was overturned. The executive branch and the judiciary cannot have equal powers and functions since the appointment of judges is a subject that is handled within the judicial family. This decision eliminated the imbalance between the executive and judicial powers that existed when judges were appointed in 1993. In the case of the jurisdiction of civil recommendations, the Supreme Court was decided in 2000. The Supreme Court was requested to provide an interpretation of this interpretation. However, did the Chief Justice of the International Court communicate with the other justices, or did he make the decision on his own? Within the context of the third judge case, the Supreme Court of India first created the collegium system. As a consequence of the decision that was handed down by the Supreme Court in 1998, a genuine collegium structure that was founded on the nine criteria was formed.

By delegation

An order to guarantee true independence of the judiciary, it is necessary for judges to perform their duties for the long term. In an event that the terms of the judges are less than ideal, there will be adverse consequences. If the judge's term is expected to be short, he will continue to run for re-election. If a judge's tenure is too short, he or she is unlikely to understand the complexities of the legal system.

Security of Service:

The executive branch must not be able to remove judges from their positions, and judges must be free to continue serving without the threat of being removed at any moment. This is necessary for the independence of the judicial system. In an event that judges are continually concerned about the possibility of losing their employment, it is difficult for them to decide against the executive branch (the government). The constitution and fundamental human rights will not be safeguarded as a consequence of this happening.

Adequate salary for the Judges:

For judges to be truly independent, they need enough money to live comfortably. Judges are drawn to the profession because of the respect and honour they receive as a result of competitive salaries and benefits.

This is due to the benefits package.

High Qualification of the Judges:

In order to maintain the independence of the judicial system, it is important that judges have the right to make the right choices and freely express their opinions. The final effect is that judges who are not competent are convinced by the arguments that are presented by the attorneys, and they end up making rulings that are incorrect.

Judiciary authority and executive control separation

In order to guarantee the independence of the court, Montesquieu underlined the need of maintaining a wall of separation between it and the executive branch. In ancient times and into the middle Ages, the executive branch exercised authority over the judicial branch. For judges to be truly independent, they need enough money to live comfortably. Judges are drawn to the profession because of the respect and honour they receive as a result of competitive salaries and benefits.

Failure to enforce the law after the break

According to article 220, under constitution "No person who has held office as a permanent Judge of a High Court shall plead or act in any court or before any authority in India except the Supreme Court and the High Court s"

Related judgments challenging the independence of the Indian judiciary in the Rafale case

DASSAULT Aviation, the French company that develops the Rafael fighter jet, recently announced a contract with the Indian government to purchase 36 of the aircraft in 2015. Through the application of the fifty per cent offset clause, the French company was required to invest fifty per cent of the total value of the contract in India by purchasing Indian products and services. According to the announcement, Reliance Group and the company will work together next year. DASSAULT said it would invest \$115 million to partially satisfy its offsetting obligations.⁶ However, the case went all the way to the Supreme Court, where the plaintiffs argued that the transaction was fraudulent. Due to the limited number of judicial reviews available in defence cases, the court decided to dismiss the corruption charges. The government challenged the court's decision, claiming it contained factual errors. The government submitted two reports to the court. One of the reports was from the Comptroller and Auditor General, and the other was from the Parliamentary Accounts Committee. Both of these reports were disregarded by the court as "misinformation." In order to put an end to the controversy, the Court decided that the petitions should be evaluated based on the merits of the cases.

Bhīma KOREGAON Incident:

Several people were injured and one person died during an event marking the 200th anniversary of the Battle of Bhīma KOREGAON in 2018. As a result of allegations that activists were instigating violence via their remarks, the police began to focus their attention on such individuals. As a consequence of this, a petition was sent to the Special inquiry Team (SIT) requesting that they conduct an inquiry into the allegations of Unlawful Activities Prevention Act that have been brought against the activists who have been imprisoned. In response to their assertion that the Mumbai Police were biased in their decision-making, the plaintiffs argued that this was not appropriate. The Supreme Court ruled in their favour and dismissed the case by a majority of 2 to 1. Unlike Chief Justice of India Deepak Mishra and Justice Khan walkers, who expressed satisfaction with the investigation conducted by the Mumbai Police, Justice by CHANDRACHUD did not find the investigation satisfactory. Judge CHANDRACHUD said that arrest was motivated by political consideration.

AADHAR the takes charge of cash account case

There was a debate on whether the AADHAR method edited from 2016 was edited in this specific case. According to most court decisions, it was a cash account. The AADDHAR Act is a money bill which can be used for such purposes as specified in section 7 of the act which states that Aadhar based authentication can be used for services or benefits which are billed to the consolidated fund of India. This section of the Act also makes it clear that the Act may be used for such purposes, although according to Article 110 of the Constitution, cash accounts can only be used for operations related to this purpose. This section of the Act also states that the Act can be used to disburse and receive money by the Union Government. In light of this, the decision was criticised by Justice CHANDRACHUD

writing for the majority, as violating the Constitution of India. In this particular instance, the judgment was delayed. As the head of the Central Bureau of Investigation

CBI ALOK VERMA CASE

Alok Verma has been deprived of all of his powers by the government. A high-ranking committee was required to provide its approval for this in accordance with the Delhi Special Police Establishment Act. Allegations of corruption were investigated by the head of the Supreme Court. The court ordered the reinstatement of Verma as director of the Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI) under the sanctions imposed by the committee. The decision to restore Verma was made despite the fact that he had just three weeks remaining on his contract term. The consequence of this was that it prompted yet another wave of criticism.

The Constitution of India:

Since its inception in Montesquieu's Doctrine at the beginning of the 18th century, the idea of judicial independence has maintained a prominent position in all contemporary democracies. The people who were responsible for drafting the Constitution of India³ came to the conclusion that it was absolutely necessary to include in the Indian Constitution measures that would create and continue to uphold judicial independence Independence of the judicial system. It has been established that the protection of the separation of powers is an essential part of the "fundamental structure. Of our constitution, which cannot be violated, The power to appoint, transfer, and other positions of subordinate judges are in the hands of the judges and the executive authority is only to appoint or give official, the instructions to the working. Regarding the appointment of Senior Judges, the President has the power to appoint those positions; he consults with the President of the Court where the appointment was made. The important position of the judge was considered by Dr. B. R. Ambedkar for India can be found in the provisions of the Constitution of India mentioned below:. Regarding the appointment of chief justices, the President has the power to appoint these positions, he

Supreme Court and Supreme Constitutional Court: Articles 124, 126, 127, 214, 216 and 217 of the Act provide for the establishment of the Supreme Court of India and the High Courts of various states and their constitution. According to Article 235, the Supreme Court has jurisdiction over the lower courts, and the Governor of the country is responsible for appointing judges to these courts and the Supreme Court.

Securing Tenure: The Judges of the Supreme Court and High Courts have been provided with the assurance that they will continue to serve in their positions. After they have been appointed, they continue to serve in their positions until they reach the age of retirement, which is 65 years for judges of the Supreme Court (Article 124(2)) and 62 years for judges of the High Courts (Article 217(1)). Only via the procedure of impeachment, which is outlined in Article 124 (4) of the Constitution, is it possible to remove a member of the higher judiciary from their position. This may be done on the basis of demonstrated misconduct or incompetence among the members of the jury.

With regard to the powers and jurisdiction of the Supreme Court, Parliament can extend the powers and jurisdiction of the Supreme Court. None of these aspects can be minimized. The storing can change the monetary threshold for appeals to the Supreme Court on civil law matters. Article 138 of the Constitution states that Parliament has the power to extend the power of the Supreme Court to make a request or to delegate power to the Supreme Court in order to improve the functioning of the Supreme Court In addition, the power to make administrative laws is vested in the Supreme Court (Article 145)..

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The Law Commission of India-

- In the 58th report of the Legal Affairs Committee, discussions on the largest judicial rights and abilities were discussed.
- The 72nd report of the Law Committee has investigated the question of whether the judge will be corrected in Article 220 of the Constitution to allow the retirement of a high court. It was a certain period, and the committee thought that the ban on the high court in front of the Supreme Court, which was a permanent judge, was one step towards insurance
- The method of appointment of judges was the subject of the Law Commission's 80th Report, which broadly accepted the constitutional scheme for the appointment of judges with some suggestions for improvement.
- The Law Commission's 95th Report proposed the creation of a Constitutional Division in the Supreme Court of India. The report also stated that the Supreme Court of India should have two divisions: the Constitutional Division and the Law Division.
- Proposals to speed up the process of filling vacancies in the High Courts and the Supreme Court and reduce the backlog of cases in these courts were the focus of the 124th and 125th reports respectively.
- The Law Commission's 195th Report was limited to examining the Judicial (Inspection) Bill, in which the Commission found that the measures envisaged in the Bill, which would ensure judicial accountability through minor measures such as notices, warnings, suspension of courts, etc., were constitutional. Furthermore, it was held that the creation of a National Judicial Council consisting only of judges was legally valid and consistent with the principles of judicial accountability, separation of powers and judicial independence. The need for a system to allow complaints to be made against all members of the High Court was reaffirmed in the following report. The 214th Report of the Law Commission addressed the necessity of revisiting the law that was established in Judges' Cases I, II, and III. The report was of the opinion that the collegium system for the appointment of judges needed to be changed. Additionally, the report stated that the government of the day had two options available to them: the first option was to seek a reconsideration of the three judgments handed down by the Supreme Court, and the second option was to pass a law that would restore the primacy of the Chief Justice of India and the power of the executive to make appointments.

Comparative and Critical Analysis

There is a very important difference between the above two methods used before the passing of the Bill and the method used after the passing of the Bill. Moreover, the involvement of the Executive in the measures governing the appointment of judges is a very important difference that must be taken into account. Because of this difference in the appointment method, we have all arrived at the point where we need to determine whether the independence of the judiciary is in jeopardy or whether this bill has posed some serious threats for the upcoming judiciary. This can be done by making an appointment with the consultation of political leaders in the collegium system. It is no exaggeration to say that this step posed a serious threat to the independence of the judiciary. The participation of non-judicial actors in the judicial system has not only corrupted and distorted the concept that the framers of the Constitution had in mind, but also undermined the provisions of the Constitution designed to achieve separation of the judiciary and the executive, and to maintain the integrity of the institution responsible for the administration of justice. As a consequence of the measure being passed in an excessively hasty manner, a great number of concerns have arisen about the reasons that led the legislature to enact this bill without engaging in any preliminary deliberations. The Bill is a piece of law that has been expertly drafted with the intention of establishing a judiciary that is bureaucratized and obedient. The government is one of the major litigants in the country, and if it were to handpick its own Supreme Court judges, there would certainly be questions of bias in the court's decisions. This is something that really needs to be understood at this point. It's going to have an impact on the veracity of the judge and the veracity of the ruling. It will then be difficult to define the judges of the Supreme Court or the High Court as independent in their conduct and in the discharge of their duties. This brings us to another

question: if this Bill is passed, how do we ensure that the very principle and fundamental features of judicial independence are upheld? It is many difficulties to find the answer to all these questions. Considering the fact that executive power plays an important role in choosing a judge, it is very difficult to specify our legal system as independent. The fact that the two commissioners have veto power would also cause great confusion: if there is a difference of opinion between the two members, no recommendation will be made. The political element of the appointments system would inevitably gravitate toward the spoils system, which is still the most widely used method regardless of party. The legality of the law that the Judicial Appointment Commission is now debating will be discussed. The nation's democracy, which is regarded as the third pillar of democracy, is at danger in addition to the judiciary's independence. This is so because the judiciary serves as the cornerstone of democracy. Even in the unlikely event that this action is upheld as lawful, the judiciary's independence is seriously jeopardized, and the third pillar of democracy is seriously threatened. This is due to the fact that implementing a system that involves Executive members in the process of nominating judges is still a very long way off.

Conclusion:

Democracy is impossible in the absence of an impartial court. This is so because the foundation of reasonable and equal justice is the judiciary. Judges can do their tasks without worrying about interference from the legislative or executive arms of government thanks to judicial independence. Judges can perform their duty without worrying about outside intervention thanks to this independence. If there is interference, the judges might not be able to reach an impartial ruling or they might base it on their own personal preferences. Judges must be appointed fairly, their terms of office should be prolonged, they must be compensated, and their removal must be extremely difficult. The independence of the court is crucial for upholding the law and protecting individual rights. The legal system is in charge of defending the people's fundamental rights since it serves as a guardian of the constitution. The judiciary must remain independent in order to successfully carry out its mandate.

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